

DIPLOMA

TA'LIM FIDOYILARI

RESPUBLIKA ILMIY JURNALIDA

Raimkulova Mekhriniso Sharif kizi

PHOENITCS AS A BRANCH OF LINGUISTICS

NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN TAQDIRLANADI

Bosh muharrir:
A.A. Abdurahmonov

2022/NOYABR

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MENTION

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